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PRIORITIES IN DATA COLLECTION FOR EUROPEAN POVERTY RESEARCH

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of live or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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1. Introduction

Poverty and social inclusion have constantly been hot topics on political and social agendas and hence the importance of survey data availability in coping with poverty is widely recognised. Empirical evidence is one of the main pillars for effective policy making. In order to study the dimensions and dynamics of poverty, and hence to take aim at reducing poverty - quality, adequacy, and timeliness of data is mission-critical. Appropriate and overarching data can bring the situation of the poor into the sight of policy makers.

The poorest and most marginalised people are usually unknown and governments have insufficient information about their living conditions. Nevertheless, they are expected to be under the radar of policy makers in order to achieve the Europe 2020 target (reduction by 20 million) as well as the Sustainable Development Goal of zero extreme poverty in the next 15 years (Granoff *et al.*, 2015). Besides administrative records and censuses, national and international surveys are significant data resources for quantitative research. Although household surveys have been on the rise both in quantity and frequency over the past 30 years, poverty data still lags behind in coverage and comparability compared to most other socio-economic data. Serajuddin *et al.* (2015) use the label of ‘data deprivation’ for the data gap in key dimensions of human and social development. In our context, we refer to the data gaps in poverty research to investigate particularly vulnerable groups - or, to put it more positively, we aim to identify priorities for data collection in the coming years.

Admittedly, great progress has been made across time and a variety of data sources are currently available. Nevertheless, research interests evolve as the ‘information frontiers’ are moving: a shift can be observed from merely descriptive research towards analysis and policy evaluation. The changes in paradigms and theoretical approaches (*e.g.* life course perspective, multilevel governance) as well as the availability of more advanced statistical techniques (longitudinal analysis, multilevel analysis etc.) boost the demand for detailed and appropriate datasets. In sum, priorities for data collection tend to shift over time, together with new trends in research, and vice versa.

The aim of this report, therefore, to provide:

- an in-depth analysis of the shifting needs for comparable data in the field of poverty and living conditions;
- conclusions for a broader, multidimensional, and forward-looking analysis of the social exclusion and inclusion processes at the national and EU levels (with special focus on specific vulnerable groups);
- an assessment of new problems in empirical research, rethinking of the key tools for data collection such as EU-SILC.

This report builds on three types of inputs:

- a selection of earlier statistical research on this topic in the European literature;
- methodological research on various vulnerable groups in poverty research, conducted in the framework of the InGRID project (Gábos & Kopasz, 2014; 2015; Schäfer *et al.*, 2015; Kopasz, 2015; Bernát & Messing, 2016; Esteve *et al.*, 2016; Schepers, Juchtmans and Nicaise, 2017; Wets, 2017). Furthermore, we made use of discussions at various expert workshops and Summer Schools on poverty research in the context of the InGRID project;

- a questionnaire survey among European experts. The questions in the survey deal mainly with the data sources that have been used, scholars' experiences, insights and proposals on feasible solutions for improving poverty data. At the end of the questionnaire, an open question was devoted to more extensive remarks and/or suggestions about this topic. Despite the low response rate (30 out of 350) from numerous European countries such as Austria (2), Belgium (4), Czech Republic (1), Germany (2), Estonia (1), Finland (1), Greece (2), Hungary (2), Ireland (3), Italy (6), Latvia (1), Poland (2), Portugal (1), Slovenia (1), we think that the answers are useful and reflect the most pressing needs of the research community. The respondents primarily used EU-SILC (mentioned by 22 scholars), but also EQLS (5), EU-LFS (5), the European Social Survey (ESS) (4), OECD Regional Well-Being Database, German Socio-Economic Panel, WHO, World Bank poverty data, European Community Household Panel (ECHP), Luxembourg Income Study (LIS), Adult Education Survey (AES), Households Budget Survey (HBS), Household Finance and Consumption Survey (HFCS), Generations and Gender Survey (GGS), European Values Survey (EVS), HBSC, ESPAD, PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, ICCS, Integrated and United the Quest for Citizenship in an Ever Closer Europe Survey (IntUne) and Survey of Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE).

We start with a summary of the expert survey (Sections 2 to 4). Then we summarise the recommendations we reached at while preparing the IPOLIS database (Section 5).

2. Potential improvements in EU-SILC – recommendations based on an expert survey

2.1 Earlier research

The European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) survey is the only source collecting timely and comparable cross-sectional and longitudinal multidimensional microdata on income, poverty, social exclusion and living conditions that covers all 28 European Union (EU) member states, as well as Iceland, Norway and Switzerland. There already exist a number of papers on the quality of the EU-SILC data, where strategies to improve the data design or to best analyse the existing data are recommended. Iacovou, *et al.* (2012) provided a comprehensive overview of strengths and weaknesses of the EU-SILC data regarding sampling and design, household dynamics, and incomes. Their findings point to several required changes with reference to data collection and provision. Verma and Betti (2006) identified a number of specific aspects where problems of comparability are likely to arise in EU-SILC, and suggested methodologies for solutions. Further recommendations on the sample design which enable estimating reliable standard errors using EU-SILC data, were brought by Goedemé (2010). Frick *et al.* (2010) argued significant differences between inequality and poverty as measured by EU-SILC for Germany and similar measures based on the well-established German Socio-Economic Panel. Last but not least, Arora *et al.* (2015) stated that one of the weaknesses of EU-SILC to be conceded is the lack of linkage between cross-sectional and longitudinal components.

2.2 Ranking of priorities

The results of our survey identify shortcomings as well as suggestions for improvement – particularly with respect to EU-SILC data, as the latter are used most widely in poverty research.

Figure 2.1 Ranking of priorities for improvement of EU-SILC data

The points on the vertical axis of Figure 2.1 correspond to the mean of evaluation points (from 0 to 10) assigned by the scholars to each item. 'Regional distribution' that corresponds to the adequacy for cross-regional research is the one, which was mentioned by most respondents and considered to be an important part of the gap. Missing information, content issues in other words, is another issue that was emphasised by our respondents. Missing topics relating to particular dimensions of living conditions are followed by sampling coverage, which was raised several times by the scholars. The rotating panel design is listed as one of the problematic features of EU-SILC as the implementation of the rule varies widely from country to country, and it is considered insufficient for high-quality longitudinal research.

Timeliness of the data delivery also deserves greater attention in poverty research, although with EU-SILC this has improved a lot in recent years. Yet, due to the operationalisation of the income concept (with reference to the calendar year preceding the survey) and the delays in releasing the data, the most recent income information available to users refers to the situation of two years ago. Shorter delays in publication of indicators are vital in monitoring the impact of policies on vulnerable groups.

Adequacy for cross-country research and metadata/documentation aspects are ranked as the last priorities.

In addition to frequently mentioned significant shortcomings, some of the respondent scholars raised other related elements to consider such as the following:

- inability to merge cross-sectional data with panel data due to different identifiers in different datasets;
- adequacy for national research in countries where SILC is about the only source of data for poverty research, i.e. lack of calibration *vis-a-vis* external major income aggregates, in other words, consistency of information on income between micro level and macro level accounts in general is lacking;
- changes to the methodology of the EU-SILC cause problems for intertemporal analysis, e.g. increasing reliance on register data and changes in variables may cause reliability and other issues for the consistency of intertemporal analysis;
- top-coding and censoring of data on income might cause problems for distribution analysis;
- reliability and quality of data on self-employment and property income are also notable concerns.

2.3 Geographical dimension

Table 2.1 summarises the feedback received from scholars in poverty research regarding the geographical dimension of EU-SILC.

EU-SILC was partly designed for the construction of indicators of poverty and social exclusion, primarily at the national level in each country. Nevertheless, as it is the main source of information on income and living conditions, this highly valued resource is expected to provide poverty indicators also for sub-national regions. As Verma and Galiardi (2010) discussed, the adequacy of national level indicators is not proven - due to lack of consistency in the definition of variables across countries. As regards the regional level, other limitations persist.

Adequacy for cross-national and cross-regional research is a key priority for EU-SILC. The importance of regional comparisons is self-evident considering the regional inequalities and distribution of poverty. Moreover, in many EU countries a multilevel governance approach is applied and many policies have been (partly) decentralised. Multilevel statistical analyses taking on board the variance at regional level may strongly enhance the power of comparative research, thanks to the large number of regions within the EU (98 regions at NUTS 1 level, 276 regions at NUTS 2 level). Unfortunately, the EU barely produces policy indicators at regional level, and moreover there are inconsistencies in data collection across regions in EU-SILC.

Table 2.1 Concerns about the geographical dimension of EU-SILC

Issues encountered (cross-country/cross-region)	Suggested solution
Consistency of information on income between micro level and macro level accounts in general, reliability of the data.	Calibration against external major income aggregates when constructing sampling weights. Such practice is in place in some countries, but not in others. Monitoring consistency between micro and macro accounts on income.
<p>Inconsistency of variable definitions across countries: variable definitions that do not completely fit with the national reality lead to blurred responses.</p> <p>For example, in Finland (where child care and preschool are integrated), most families with children below the compulsory school age filled out information about formal child care while for pre-school there were many missing values.</p> <p>Other example: some information is not reported in all countries (population density, net income, etc.).</p>	Variables should be better harmonised across countries and interpreted more precisely in each country.
<p>Important national/regional context and policy indicators are often not available and/or not comparable.</p> <p>Examples: taxes and benefits, labour market institutions, educational policies, family policies, etc.</p>	Production of indicators (from other sources) at regional level.
<p>Lack of LAU 1 and 2 variables.</p> <p>Lack of regional NUTS 2 identifiers.</p>	Release this information in the EU-SILC standard file.
<p>Small sample sizes make it difficult to do analysis on (detailed) regional level.</p> <p>Under-representation of subnational levels/urban and rural residence.</p>	<p>Increased sample size.</p> <p>Regional stratification.</p>

The most frequently encountered and reported issue for comparative research is the lack of regional identifiers at NUTS 2 level (LAU 1 and 2). In most cases the information is included in the national data sets, but deleted by Eurostat. The absence of sub-national geographical information also results

in under-representation of subnational levels and the urban-rural inequalities in research. Furthermore, important regional policy indicators are often not available or not comparable; and (in)consistency of information on income between micro level and macro level accounts in general, is a major concern in relation to the reliability of the data. Suggested solutions include using regional identifiers, increasing regionally-built sample size, using data from domestic research, appending regional policy indicators and calibrating microdata against macro-aggregates.

2.4 Content Issues

Many issues of great importance to poor people (Alkire, 2007) are left out of surveys. This is understandable given the trade-off between response rates and length of questionnaires. More generally, there is a trade-off between extending the questionnaire by adding new topics and the validity of the data, also considering resource-side constraints (in terms of money and time). Nevertheless, as research priorities are shifting, it may be worth considering to reduce the weight of existing topics¹ in favour of newer ones - and/or to include the newer topics into ad-hoc modules. In some countries, part of the information can be drawn from administrative registers, which opens opportunities to replace sets of questions. Alternatively, new topics can be covered in other surveys, provided the latter are also relevant to poverty research. However, when the introduction of new topics is planned, it should be always considered whether it is worthwhile to do it with the existing sample sizes. For some specific topics or when sub-group/geographical area specific analysis is in focus, national sample sizes may put a strong barrier to the use of such information.

Our respondents pointed at a number of themes whose inclusion would strengthen EU-SILC, improve poverty measures and enable deeper analysis and better understanding of poverty. New topics deserve attention as poverty research is shifting from measurement and description (poverty profiling) to analysis of processes and determinants of in-/exclusion. A further shift from analysis to policy evaluation should produce insights into the effectiveness of anti-poverty policies in particular.

¹ Unfortunately, our questionnaire did not include questions on items that could be deleted or simplified in EU-SILC.

Table 2.2 Missing themes/clusters of variables

Missing topic	Should be in yearly survey	Should be a special module
More financial information : wealth, savings and debts, fixed/recurrent expenditure (<i>e.g.</i> mortgage repayments, child care costs, etc.)		x
Financial inclusion module introduced in 2008 should be repeated with the more detailed questions regarding access/reasons for not having etc.		x
Time use components – <i>e.g.</i> caring responsibilities		x
Capabilities/resources/multi-dimensional poverty indicators: skills, material wealth, material & social deprivation indicators such as in ECHP, health, disabilities, social networks, living environment, ... The present information in EU-SILC is too limited	x	x
More detailed labour market information : Job values, 'soft' job characteristics, entrepreneurial potential (inclination and intention), migration potential		x
Participation in the active labour market policies,	x	
Use of social media (Facebook, Twitter, etc.)	x	
Social participation/social networks	x	
Education careers of children (preschool period, school success, learning difficulties, type of school, field of study, diplomas , ...)/learning of adults	x	x
Social-psychological dimension of well-being/social cohesion - perceptions, attitudes, feelings: <i>e.g.</i> trust in people, acceptance of diversity, attitudes toward immigration, trust in institutions, views about elites, solidarity and helpfulness, human dignity, social justice, social power/influence, collective identities, life satisfaction, perceived and/or objective difficulties/discrimination experienced due to being a member of a particular disadvantaged group (gender, age, ethnicity, ...)		
Use of/benefits from social policy measures (active labour market policies, social services, lifelong learning, public housing, ...)	x	
Use, accessibility and affordability of services of general interest : social (<i>e.g.</i> ECEC, education, health care, etc.) as well as material (energy, water, housing, public transport, internet, telecom, ...)	x	
Intergenerational and life course perspective : Parental background, Intergenerational/inter-household transfers, children out of household (<i>e.g.</i> placed in care, or social destination of young adults who left the household), transition into the labour market		x

When looking at the main missing thematic clusters (see Table 2.2) and missing variables (see Table 2.3) mentioned by experts, the priorities appear to fall under several thematic clusters. To start with, one of the remarkable content issues is the key drivers of *socio-economic mobility* such as (parental) socio-economic background, education careers of children and financial or asset flows - in particular wealth, debt, recurrent expenditures (*e.g.* utilities), and intergenerational/-household transfers. Secondly, more details about *labour market participation*, time use components – *e.g.* caring obligations etc. would enrich the capacity of poverty research data. Several scholars express the need to broaden the perspective to a ‘*capabilities*’ approach, or at least a more multidimensional approach giving greater weight to non-financial resources such as skills, disability, health, social networks, access to public services etc. A related priority relates to the *benefits from policy measures* and use of services of general interest such as active labour market measures, child care, public housing, social services, social media, etc. Material services of general interest are also important instruments of anti-poverty policies. The survey should include factual information on the use, cost, cuts, as well as user satisfaction about their quality. *Social-psychological variables* and *cultural attitudes* such as trust, diversity, solidarity, well-being, discrimination, etc. are also mentioned repeatedly. There is a strong overlap between Tables 2.2 and 2.3, with Table 2.2 ranging more widely and Table 2.3 proposing some more detailed items.

Table 2.3 Missing (single) variables

<p>Disaggregated benefits by type, <i>e.g.</i> contributory/ non-contributory; means-tested/non-means-tested (Eligibility for) welfare assistance on a monthly basis 'Non-cash' income (fringe benefits, in-kind support) Durations of benefit receipt when information from registers, rather than survey-based accounts, is used Deprivation indicators used in Coromaldi and Zoli 2012 (Deriving multidimensional poverty indicators: Methodological issues and an empirical analysis for Italy) Deprivation indicators used in Bossert <i>et al.</i> 2009 (Multidimensional poverty and material deprivation with discrete data) Details on second/third job Details on occupational changes in reference to occupational/ educational attainment Sector of employment - private or public Detailed labour market contract data Type of contract for LM monthly information (temporary versus permanent) Ask if person currently at work earns the minimum wage (below or above) Ask when they last worked (after PL015 ever worked) and why left job? Trade union membership Distinguish public pension from occupational pension Composition and increase/decrease of household debt (bank credit, social security, tax, utilities, family & friends, etc.) Inter-household transfers paid/received (certain values 1: children, 2: parents, 3: siblings, 4: other relatives, 5: friends): volume, frequency, reasons, type (grant, alimony, inheritance, formal/informal loan, ...) Did the household go into debt within the last 12 months to meet ordinary living expenses such as mortgage repayments, rent, food or back-to-school expenses? (discrete data) More variables about absolute poverty At-risk-of-poverty indicator associated with indicators on greenhouse gas emissions and land use at NUTS level 2</p>
<p>Resilience of social networks Having a Facebook account (yes/no) Frequency of the use of Facebook Having a Twitter account (yes/no) Frequency of the use of Twitter Having other social network account (yes/no) Frequency of the use of other social network</p>
<p>Level of trust in other people Acceptance of individuals with other values and lifestyles Level of confidence in social and political institutions Level of felt responsibility for other people A direct question on overall life satisfaction or happiness Mental health measure (WHO-5) General Life Satisfaction Details on (in)dependency of living Variables measuring aspirations Variables measuring social distance Personality traits Gender disparities</p>
<p>Level and grade of education of school-going children Field of study (usage of education at current job) Particular details on household with children If household members have a medical cover and what type Did people had to wait for health care (waiting lists)? Parental education (yearly) Details on child and elderly care Details on parental occupation, education and wealth Trade unions in employment and participation</p>

2.5 The panel dimension

Besides being a valuable tool for cross-sectional comparison, another advantage of EU-SILC data is the longitudinal design of the dataset. The EU-SILC includes both a longitudinal and cross-sectional

component. This is achieved by organising the EU-SILC as a rotating panel study in which households are interviewed in four consecutive years (Eurostat, 2013: 19). Panel data allow research to (a) distinguish between short-term and persistent poverty, (b) to analyse income mobility from a life-course perspective, and more recently, (c) to study the impact of short-term relief measures compared to longer-term social investments on well-being, possibly also in multiple dimensions. The life-course perspective draws attention to the effectiveness of social policies in preventing, coping or promoting specific life events, turning points and transitions between life stages. The social investment perspective is also expected to address the ‘new social risks’ faced by citizens in a post-industrial society (Armingeon and Bonoli, 2006) such as lack of qualification, family breakdown, etc.

Besides, the EC has promoted the use of *social impact assessment* of (other than social) policies as a means to monitor the coherence between the economic and social objectives of the Union (the so-called ‘horizontal social clause’, art. 9 of the TFEU). Impact assessment is a policy-related activity; consequently time and resources are critical constraints, and the use of rich longitudinal datasets is essential for this purpose.

According to the InGRID survey results, some crucial elements of panel data are deemed to be incomplete. EU-SILC cross-sectional data and longitudinal datasets have differently named identifiers, which becloud the combination of those different datasets. As a consequence, variables in the cross-sectional data files that are also of interest for the analysis of labour market transitions and mobility are not included in the longitudinal data sets. Clémenceau and Museux (2007) confirm that the longitudinal data are limited in variables and also more limited in sample size. Withal, some primary sampling units in the EU-SILC longitudinal dataset are missing, although ‘it is possible to infer cluster indicators from previous years for which data are available in most cases’ (Goedemé, 2010).

Cross-sectional and longitudinal components of EU-SILC are packaged separately, hence linkage between cross-sectional and longitudinal elements would be feasible provided of a unique identifier is used in both datasets (Arora *et al.*, 2015). Iacovou *et al.* (2012) state that the EU-SILC in its current form is not appropriate for analysing transitions for some of the groups of most interest to social scientists: young adults and separating couples.

Table 2.4 Concerns about the longitudinal EU-SILC dataset

Issues encountered (longitudinal)	Suggested solution
<p>Small sample sizes</p> <p>Lack of clear guidelines on the construction and use of the longitudinal weights in EU-SILC</p> <p>Too short time window of the panel (4 years). Very difficult to study poverty or unemployment transitions controlling for state or duration dependence. Impossible to study inter-generational poverty issues.</p> <p>Lack of EU-level longitudinal data in general</p> <p>Construction of panel data is difficult</p> <p>Level of attrition between waves for some countries makes it impossible to study income mobility over time</p> <p>Spurious panel data</p> <p>Dataset design: What is the logic behind dataset provided under yearly label? It is very unclear: for example, why does the dataset for 2014 include observations for individuals who are not present in 2014?</p> <p>How to merge cross-sectional information with longitudinal? There are many variables which can be useful for longitudinal studies, and they are gathered in cross-sectional data, why cannot we link them, while they are already collected?</p>	<p>Increase sample sizes</p> <p>Improve documentation of the longitudinal data</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Increase the length of the panel component 2) Include retrospective questions/control variables that capture initial conditions <i>e.g.</i> poverty in childhood for adults or questions about initial education, parents, grand-parents + experiencing economic hardship or unemployment in the period before the 4 years’ time-window. <p>Collect more longitudinal data</p> <p>Full panels instead of rotating panels</p> <p>Reduce the level of attrition.</p> <p>Create a ‘real’ panel of respondents for more than 4 periods in appropriate sample size</p> <p>Clear and harmonised description of dataset provided, including the causes of attrition (no contact, refusal, leaving the household, etc.); better meta-information about dataset</p> <p>Use of harmonised identifier making the link possible.</p>

Feedback from poverty researchers (see the details in Table 2.4 above) refers to the following main data gaps in longitudinal research with EU-SILC:

- lack of panels across the board;
- the rotating panel structure of EU-SILC, which is found to be ‘too small, too short’ and;
- to involve unnecessary complexities in combining cross-section and panel data (SILC).

The most convenient solution to start with would be the inclusion of harmonised identifiers to facilitate merging cross-sectional and longitudinal datasets.

2.6 Coverage Issues: hard-to-survey groups

Household surveys fail to cover as many as 350 million people worldwide (Stuart, *et al.*, 2015). In particular, vulnerable groups such as homeless people, travellers, people living in institutions, ethnic minorities, refugees and asylum seekers often remain invisible due to social and political underrepresentation. The consequences can be cruel. Carr-Hill (2013) argues that due to being missed-out from surveys, the number of people living in absolute poverty could be underestimated by a quarter.

In European poverty research too, immigrants, refugees or ethnic minorities, homeless people, nomads, travellers, Roma, etc. are frequently mentioned as hard-to-survey groups (Kalton, 2014; Nicaise & Schockaert, 2014; Bernát & Messing, 2016; Schepers, Juchtmans & Nicaise, 2017; Wets, 2017). The underrepresented groups in EU-SILC pertain to different hard-to-survey groups, for various reasons:

- some of them are *hard-to-sample* because they are very small minorities or are not even included in the sampling framework. EU-SILC measures incomes at the level of *private* households drawn from population registers (based on their official residence address). Hence, it excludes a priori collective households (such as prisons, care and health institutions and refugee shelters), homeless people, undocumented immigrants and (partly) nomadic populations. This sampling design also inevitably leads to an underrepresentation of other high-risk groups living in collective households (*e.g.* the elderly and persons with disabilities or mental health problems);
- some groups are also *hard-to-contact*, even if they are included in EU-SILC samples. This obviously applies to itinerant groups – even supposing they have an official residence. In the case of undocumented immigrants, fear of being caught is an additional obstacle. Roma and travellers may also be hard-to-contact due to stigma, social exclusion and distrust against the mainstream society. In a rotating panel design, many other groups experiencing poverty show a higher risk of attrition due to their precarious housing situation (frequent moves, evictions);
- a third category of hard-to-survey groups are *hard-to-interview*, even if they can be reached and willing to collaborate. Migrants are typically underrepresented in EU-SILC due to language barriers. Interviews with low-literate persons or people with mental health problems are more often interrupted than with other households. We suspect that the complexity of EU-SILC questionnaires cause a lot of interruptions, item non-response or unreliable data.

Unsurprisingly, under-coverage of hard-to-survey groups is mentioned by almost all respondents in our survey. In order to overcome such under-coverage challenges, researchers need to carefully consider the aim and the design of their research and anticipate some social, psychological and ethical issues (building trust and gaining consent of vulnerable groups), even before taking any steps in contacting households. Furthermore, the complex and multi-layered nature of the difficulties discussed above requires multiple, multidimensional and innovative strategies or approaches, not just by showing respect for the respondents in an instrumental way (*i.e.* in order to obtain valid data), but also by investing additional resources in outreaching (*e.g.* tracking when addresses appear to be incorrect,

more frequent contact attempts, face-to-face interviewing rather than written survey methods), making the survey more feasible (*e.g.* by simplifying questionnaires and translating them in minority languages) and training interviewers to enhance their patience, empathy and motivation to give their respondents voice and visibility in society.

The problems in collecting high-quality data from hard-to-survey populations are diverse and often interrelated. Non-response, coverage error and undercounts are measurement errors that can emerge in all types of research. For researchers on hard-to-survey populations it is important to be aware of these sources of error, as well as the methods to minimise them.

Among the suggested solutions to overcome underrepresentation, the most commonsensical ones are using translated questionnaires, implementing quota sampling, oversampling of immigrants and conducting ‘satellite surveys’ using dual sampling frameworks.

Nicaise and Schockaert (2014) successfully experimented with the design and implementation of ‘satellite surveys’ among hard-to-survey groups such as homeless people and undocumented immigrants in Belgium, using a simplified SILC questionnaire, administered to specific samples drawn via indirect sampling methods (more precisely, via services or organisations working with those target groups). These surveys allowed the authors to produce detailed profiles of different target groups that can be compared with other EU-SILC samples. They suggest that such satellite surveys be carried out in a more systematic way (though not yearly) across the EU, so that the living conditions of different subgroups of socially excluded people can be compared between countries and monitored across time. Admittedly, these satellite surveys involve a higher cost per unit, and a panel design is probably not feasible. Instead, co-ordinated five-yearly surveys using specific sampling techniques, in collaboration with services targeting these groups, seem to make up a feasible investment yielding interesting results.

During each stage of the planning, there may be new insights about the feasibility of the survey design, leading to repeated revisions of the research goals, the definition of the target population, the questionnaire, sampling design, training procedures, mode choice, and so on. Ideally, the design chosen should be one that produces estimates with the smallest possible mean squared errors. This criterion leads to a design that takes all major error sources into account. This implies that any organisation conducting surveys must have a system for quality assurance and quality control in place.

Research strategies to overcome trust barriers between researchers and respondents in poverty research include (community-based) participatory research, recruiting peer researchers, data collectors or interviewers, providing training, support and supervision for interviewers, developing culturally appropriate questionnaires and innovative data collection methods, such as non-verbal methods and methods using digital technology. When applied thoroughly, these strategies enhance communicative success with hard-to-reach groups living in poverty and thus increase the validity of research results. However, it has to be noted that successful implementation of these strategies can only exist by virtue of sufficient budget and good mutual and well-maintained relationships between survey teams and services or (self-)advocacy groups working with disadvantaged groups.

3. Other datasets than EU-SILC

3.1 Issues relating to specific datasets

The experiences and remarks of researchers on other data sources are summarised in Table 3.1. Specific experiences with other EU microdata sets revealed that, so far, all of them involve specific problems. The ESS is not comparable with EU-SILC due to the inadequate measurement of labour income, non-cash income/wealth and not having a panel structure. The EU-LFS appears to suffer from problems with its panel dimension. To be more specific, the identifiers that allow merging individuals over time are not available by the Eurostat. Moreover, the EU-LFS is not only difficult to access, but moreover its health module is not harmonised with EU-SILC and EHIS. Suggestions for improving the comparability of EU-SILC and EU-LFS include the following: using similar instruments in defining main items (health, activity limitations etc.), asking the details of the unemployment period such as reason of losing the job, obstacles of not finding a job, etc. in the survey and link the employed respondents with the administrative registers, allowing access to tracking respondents in the panel and collect more data, such as earnings and ethnicity (possibly in the outgoing rotation). Last but not least, EQLS dataset includes wide range of variables and valuable information however one of the challenges for comparative analysis (in particular regarding education related questions) is ambiguity in questions such as unstandardised definitions of terms, i.e. 'child care'.

As regards the use of regional context and policy indicators in combination with microdata, both the OECD and the World Bank are potential sources, However, the geographical matching with the European NUTS 1-2 classification is imperfect.

Table 3.1 Experiences with other European/international datasets used in poverty research

Data source	Experiences	Perspectives for future research	Obstacles
EU-LFS	Large samples allow for more detailed and reliable estimates	More extensive use of the longitudinal structure of EU-LFS data	Panel component of EU-LFS has restricted access and has too few variables (<i>e.g.</i> ethnicity, earnings)
FRA datasets	Rich data collected via FRA surveys in several crucial areas of human rights and human experiences. Respondents regret that these datasets are not accessible to external researchers for secondary analysis.	The FRA datasets could also be made public.	Problems with sample design.
Country level counterparts of EU datasets	More detailed information, less categorisation.		Problems with access.
OECD Regional Well-Being Database	Compound indicators, also show evolution per 5-year periods.	Interesting indicators for regional analysis – to be aligned with Eurostat data and NUTS territories	OECD regions do not always correspond to NUTS-Regions
World Bank poverty data	Indicators on education, poverty and equity, governance, health nutrition, gender, jobs etc.	Interesting indicators for regional analysis – to be regionalised and aligned with Eurostat data and NUTS territories.	Mostly only available at country level

3.2 Streamlining between surveys

The respondents to our survey also used various other datasets, mainly the European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS), the European Union Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS), and the European Social Survey (ESS). It is worth noting that Eurostat is working on streamlining the EU-SILC, the Adult Education Survey (AES) and the LFS. In the first instance, streamlining means *harmonisation* of variables. Indeed, if some key (socio-demographic and/or income) variables could be harmonised across surveys, this would at least allow for matched statistical tables covering a wider range of poverty dimensions.

A possible future scenario could result in *integration* of these three surveys by means of unique individual identifiers. Integration of surveys in general, and anonymised integration of survey data with register data/big data are mentioned by several poverty research scholars as promising avenues for more efficient data collection. Whereas the former (combining two or more surveys) may yield ‘informational economies of scope’, the combined questionnaires may also enhance the burden for respondents and thus reduce response rates, particularly among low-literate groups. Hence, it seems preferable to harmonise - rather than integrate - surveys.

By contrast, linking surveys with register data could *reduce* the burden of surveys by reducing the length of questionnaires; it can also enhance the range of disposable information, and/or enable longitudinal research which is otherwise unfeasible (for example, by linking survey data with subsequent work career data, or indeed with mortality from administrative data).

Data protection laws often hinder linkages between datasets. The mere fact that respondents need to authorise such linkages may enhance non-response. Nevertheless, some countries have developed specific protocols that facilitate such linkages specifically for the sake of scientific research.

3.3 Longitudinal data

In view of the general complaint about the lack of EU-wide panel data, the perspective of a possible longitudinal cohort study funded by the European Commission (explored under the MYWEB project) should be applauded. As child poverty is on the rise in the EU, and given the key role of investments in early childhood, it is important to develop the statistical tools that are necessary to evaluate the impact of policies targeted at disadvantaged children.

3.4 Timeliness

Timeliness of data delivery is essential for the monitoring and evaluation of policy reforms. There are several factors that affect timeliness of the data such as duration and timing of fieldwork, different time references in different questions, and the retrospective measurement of income data provided to Eurostat. For future research, the problem can be circumvented in several ways:

- speeding up the data delivery to shorten the delays for access;
- producing ‘flash’ estimates in particular for deprivation indicators (ignoring the income dimension); and;
- for the impact assessment of policy measures, the use of ‘now-casting’ (forecasting the impact by means of simulation). The EUROMOD project has produced excellent tools for this approach - mainly designed to estimate the distributional effects of tax-benefit reforms. Both the European Commission and some Member States are already making use of now-casting methods in *ex-ante* evaluations of reforms.

3.5 Harmonisation across countries

One of the shortcomings in poverty research is that some data are not really comparable across countries. Datasets differ from each other with respect to harmonisation methods. For instance, most surveys co-ordinated by Eurostat yield output-harmonised data sets, whereas the ESS, SHARE, ECHP, are input-harmonised - with questionnaires that were designed to be comparable across countries at the outset. As Mack (2016) summarised, output harmonisation can be defined as the approach where the participating (national) statistical institutes agree on a set of target variables, which are described in the Methodological guidelines and description of target variables² and a number of quality criteria in regards to data collection³ without elaborating joint questionnaires or agreeing on all details of the sampling and data collection protocols. Accordingly, output-harmonised datasets are less reliable as a resource for making cross-national comparisons than a similar input-harmonised dataset would be. Some aspects to be given careful consideration relate to differences in sampling and weighting procedures, documentation of datasets, different approaches to data collection, divergent wording of questionnaires, and last but not the least different reference periods. A meta-analysis of the 2012 wave of the Adult Education Survey (AES) illustrates this problem: it involves serious problems of comparability due to divergent formulation of the country questionnaires (Lavrijsen & Nicaise, 2015).

3.6 Other Issues

The respondents in our survey complained that the poor metadata on sampling design and variables result in a waste of research time and unreliable research findings. ‘Amputation’ of data due to obsession with privacy or political sensitivity was mentioned numerous times by the respondents as being an obstacle for the analysis, causing a loss of precision. In the name of data protection and privacy significant portions of data get lost due to categorisation of continuous variables, deletion of important variables, restricted access to data, etc.

² Commonly referred to as ‘Guidelines’ (Eurostat, 2013).

³ Defined in Commission Regulation No 28/2004.

4. Conclusions of the expert survey: potential benefits of better data

If we want to move poverty and inequalities higher on the policy agenda, accurate and timely statistical information is of utmost importance. It helps in identifying priority groups and dimensions, estimating the scope and budget cost of interventions, monitoring progress and evaluating the impact of policy measures. Contributing to the improvement of the data infrastructure for poverty research was one of the remits of the InGRID project.

EU-SILC is the most important data source that provides objective performance indicators on income, poverty, inequality and living conditions in Europe. This paper identifies a number of possible improvements in its content, geographical structure, representativeness for population groups with a high poverty risk and longitudinal design.

As regards the content of EU-SILC, we would mainly suggest:

- (a) to widen the focus from a predominantly financial approach to a genuine multidimensional capabilities approach,
- (b) with more attention to the social-psychological and cultural dimension of inequality and social cohesion, and
- (c) the citizens' use and assessment of the quality of services and policies.

The trade-off between length of the questionnaires and response rates obviously needs to be monitored carefully. Several solutions can be envisaged: cutting back on questions relating to the financial dimension; linking the survey with administrative register data; designing ad hoc modules that are not repeated yearly; or gathering the proposed data through a variety of surveys (including *e.g.* EQLS, Eurobarometer, LFS, etc.).

The geographical scale of EU-SILC, covering more than 30 countries, opens a lot of opportunities for comparative research. However, the validity of such research depends crucially on the comparability of data, which is not always guaranteed given the 'output-harmonisation' of data. To begin with, a systematic meta-analysis should contribute to a public pool of metadata documenting the strengths and weaknesses of EU-SILC. In the future, the questionnaires themselves should be co-ordinated more rigorously.

As many social policies have been devolved to the regional level, comparative statistical analysis should increasingly take that multi-level governance into account. To begin with, regional identifiers in EU-SILC should be included or kept in the data sets (they are currently often available in national datasets, but then deleted by Eurostat). Multilevel statistical analysis does not necessarily require that the data are representative for every single region. Yet, if the aim is to ensure that representativeness, the samples will need to be designed accordingly. Moreover, Eurostat needs to produce regional context and policy indicators so as to enable research to examine the impact of policies.

The absence – or severe under-representation of population groups with a high poverty risk is a serious challenge for the reliability of EU-SILC-based statistics. We think that the data would be substantially improved in terms of coverage of hard-to-survey groups, if data collection protocols are designed accordingly (translated and adapted questionnaires; quota sampling; face-to-face interview-

ing of low-literate groups; special training of interviewers) and satellite surveys are designed for specific excluded groups such as homeless people, undocumented immigrants, travellers etc. using dual and indirect sampling frameworks.

The dynamics of inequality and poverty necessitate an improved longitudinal design of EU-SILC. Although the present rotating panel structure is useful for relatively simple intertemporal analyses, it suffers from two major flaws: (a) too short time windows for the study of long-term effects of (social investment) policies, let alone, of long-term or intergenerational mobility patterns; (b) loss of information due to disconnection between cross-sectional and longitudinal datasets. Whereas the former problem would necessitate an ambitious extension of the panel, the latter can in principle be solved quickly without additional cost.

Our survey also yielded some noteworthy suggestions concerning other European datasets such as the LFS, EQLS etc. Many suggestions that were put forward for EU-SILC also apply to these other surveys. Moreover, harmonisation of the socio-economic questionnaire modules across surveys, or indeed integration of surveys and integration of survey data with register data are expected to generate enormous economies of scale in data collection as well as in statistical analysis. Timeliness which is essential for M&E of policy reforms; better quality metadata and efficient solutions to reconcile scientific interest with privacy protection are priorities for further improvement.

5. Recommendations regarding indicators for specific vulnerable groups

In what follows we summarise the specific findings and suggestions regarding various specific vulnerable groups. Some overlaps with previous suggestions may pertain. However, a cross cutting summary of data issues may also be useful for specialists of the various social policy target groups.

5.1 Children

The Child module of IPOLIS, based on the QoL concept was elaborated in the ICP. While IPOLIS is enabling tool for stakeholders to better understand social processes related to vulnerability, to stay informed, and to find empirical evidences for their questions, the preparation brought up a number of scientific, methodological and data infrastructure issues. These recommendations formulated on the basis of the preparation process are addressed to the Commission, which shall take leadership in further improving the conditions of a better monitoring system of vulnerable groups, including children.

In the selection of indicators for the Child module of IPOLIS, of the potential data sources we preferred surveys conducted in the total population or in children. Similarly to SPC (2012), we relied primarily on EU-SILC. As was seen, EU-SILC served as the main data source for the domains ‘material living conditions’, ‘labour market attachment and work-life balance’, and ‘environmental quality and physical safety’. Beside EU-SILC, a number of indicators were extracted from PISA and PIRLS for the domain ‘education and training’; from HBSC for the domains ‘health and risk behaviours’ and ‘social connectedness and civic participation’; and from ESPAD for the domain ‘health and risk behaviours’. EHIS and LFS, key sources of data in the SPC, were not used in the child module of IPOLIS, since the relatively low number of observations in the relevant age group (15-17 year-olds) may reduce the robustness of indicators.

5.1.1 Encouraging the extension of child monitoring in terms of quality of life domains and components

When setting up the Child module of IPOLIS, we found that the potential pool of policy relevant, timely, cross-country comparable and robust indicators is large and the underlying data infrastructure is rich in regard to some QoL domains (*e.g.* ‘material living conditions’ and ‘health and risk behaviours’). In the case of some other domains and components (*e.g.* ‘social connectedness and civic participation’ and ‘environmental quality and physical safety’), the indicator coverage and the data infrastructure are poorer. In all cases, however, we identified important gaps, indicating that there is some room to further improve the monitoring process. In what follows we list the main data gaps by domain and provide some recommendations for improving the available cross-national data on children.

5.1.2 Material living conditions

The domain ‘material living conditions’ is properly represented in the Child module of IPOLIS. We selected the most important measures out of the available pool of indicators, also taking into consideration the criteria of keeping balance across domains and components. Dynamic indicators of deprivation, as well as composite measures (beyond the existing EU2020 fight against poverty and social exclusion target) shall complete the proposed set of measures when the methodological development work will have been completed and the European Commission will have accepted them in the Social OMC portfolio.

- Survey data on material living conditions are abundant. All the information needed to compute these indicators is provided at household level, by the household reference person. This means that the same information is attached to each household member, irrespective of whether they are adults or children (even though an equivalence scale is applied to account for the economies of scale in consumption).
- One way to strengthen the child perspective would be to collect data on children’s reflections to their material conditions, including financial resources, consumption and housing conditions. To some extent, the EU-SILC 2009 module and the proposal for a new material deprivation indicator touch upon this problem and make a step further, by including child-specific indicators of material conditions beside household level measures. This information is provided for all children aged 1-15 by the household reference person (basically one of the parents). Either the parent or the child is the respondent, the problems of validity and reliability of data can be raised in both cases. Present data reported by parents seem to suggest that in Europe children’s material living conditions, on average, are better than those of the overall households (Guio, Gordon & Marlier, 2013).

5.1.3 Education and training

The inclusion of the indicator of ECEC access is of major importance. ECEC services may help break the transmission of disadvantage across generations and afford all children the opportunity to reach their full potential (SPC, 2012: 21). At the Barcelona Summit in 2002, the European Council set the targets of providing child care by 2010 to at least 90% of children between three years old and the mandatory school age and at least 33% of children under 3 years of age, while the European Education and Training 2020 benchmark on early childhood education participation is that by 2020 at least 95% of children aged between birth and the age for starting compulsory primary education should participate in early childhood education (SPC, 2012: 22). It would highly improve the monitoring of early ages if measures of quality of ECEC, of different child developmental outcomes (*e.g.* physical health and well-being, cognitive skills, emotional maturity, social competence) and of family satisfaction were to complete the indicator of access to these types of services.

- According to its definition, the early school-leaving indicator is computed for those aged 18-24, which life period belongs to the youth, and thus we shifted it to the Youth module of IPOLIS. However, the indicator refers in fact to processes during childhood. At national level, there would certainly be better measures available, based on school level administrative data. These data would allow for a continuous monitoring of the drop out processes by grades. Therefore the lack of an indicator for the component ‘early school leaving’ is related to the comparability of national education systems and the lack of available and comparable data to provide measures that indicate or predict final drop-outs in an earlier phase of childhood. The data infrastructure related to the ‘education and training’ domain is relatively large and beside administrative data it includes child-centred cross-country comparative surveys. Beyond problems related to country coverage, which are discussed in more detail below, one difficulty is related to periodicity at which the relevant indicators can be produced in a reliable way. The three-year periodicity in PISA becomes in fact a nine-year periodicity when one aims to go beyond the most basic indicators: the OECD publishes regular

statistics, like differences in mean test-scores according family background, only at this nine year periodicity for each of the competencies.

5.1.4 Health and risk behaviours

The domain ‘health and risk behaviours’ is one of the most documented QoL domains. Yet, some data gaps should be mentioned concerning the ‘health status’ and ‘health behaviours’ components.

- There are no data on the objective health status of children, except for the perinatal period and the first year of life.
- Only sporadic data are available on the mental health status of children. Adolescents themselves are asked about their mental health status only in ESPAD.
- Data on health behaviours (nutrition, personal care, physical activity and obesity) are available only for children aged 11 to 15 (or in case of obesity 13 to 15) from the HBSC survey, while some health behaviour patterns or problems may emerge in younger ages. This may be the case with overweight and obesity. Childhood obesity is a high priority issue and the overarching goal of the new Action Plan on Childhood Obesity⁴ is to contribute to halting the rise in overweight and obesity in children and young people (0-18 years) by 2020. Therefore, it is very important to better monitor overweight and obesity in childhood. Since the reliability of self-reported height and weight data is questionable, harmonised objective measurement would be more suitable for monitoring and policy intervention.

5.1.5 Social connectedness and civic participation

The data infrastructure on children’s family and peer relationships seems to be sufficient. However, there is a lack of data on children’s relationships with others than parents or peers (*e.g.* members of the extended family, other adults outside of school) (Richardson, 2012: 91). Two child surveys collect data regularly on children’s relationships with their parents: HBSC and ESPAD. These surveys, along with PIRLS and TIMSS, are also the main sources of data on peer relationships. Although the formation of close attachments to family and peers has been linked to healthy youth development in numerous studies, we currently lack regular indicators on relationships with parents and peers. While indicators of family and peer relationships (the latter mainly in terms of bullying) are included in some of the reviewed child well-being indicator systems, this component of children’s quality of life is neglected in SPC (2012).

It is pronounced in SPC (2012) that children’s participation in social, recreational, sporting and cultural activities is crucial to the promotion of a child’s development because it enhances self-confidence as well as social and civic skills. However, as the SPC points out, the lack of systematic and comparable data on children’s participation is a significant barrier to integrate this domain into the child specific poverty and well-being indicator systems (SPC, 2012: 10). Of the different forms of children’s participation it is civic participation that the Child module of IPOLIS focuses on.

Currently, the only source of data on children’s civic participation is the ICCS survey. It asks students aged 13 to 14 years to state whether they participated in the activity of organisations of different kinds, including youth organisations affiliated with a political party or union, environmental organisations, human rights organisations, voluntary groups doing something to help the community, organisations collecting money for a social cause, cultural organisations based on ethnicity, and groups or young people campaigning for an issue. The first wave of the survey was conducted in 2008-2009, but up to now no information is available about the planned date of the second wave.

⁴ The ‘EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity 2014-2020’ was adopted in 2014.

5.1.6 Environmental quality and physical safety

‘Environmental quality and physical safety’ is probably the domain we know the least about, with special regard to the ‘environmental quality’ component.

The majority of data on local environmental quality come from household surveys (and thus asked from adults). EU-SILC provides some data on environmental pollution in the locality. The questionnaire contains one specific question about noise and one general about environmental problems. This latter question is asked about all possible complaints in the local area, including air pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry. Unfortunately, based on this comprehensive question, the environmental problem that may affect children’s quality of life cannot be identified.

There are no questions in the EU-SILC about other aspects of the locality that may affect children’s quality of life *e.g.* green spaces, access to spaces for recreational activities, etc. As Richardson (2012) points out, questions about the local environment from the perspective of children could be strengthened including children’s facilities in the area.

Finally, indoor pollution (*e.g.* smoking in the home) is absolutely neglected in the surveys, however, may have harmful effects on children’s health.

5.1.7 Extending child monitoring to children not or only weakly represented by the current system and the underlying data infrastructure

We recommend the inclusion of groups of children that are not captured by the present data collection, and of those that are supposed to be captured, but in fact are not fully captured. Three main issues should be discussed here.

5.1.7.1 Age coverage

Children’s own responses in each dimension are completely missing before the age of 9. Household surveys can be used to breakdown age-related experiences by dimension, although this information is provided by parents or guardians (Richardson 2012: 101). The lack of internationally comparable survey-derived and representative data on children under the age of 9 raises the possibility of a new international survey of pre-primary school children (Richardson 2012: 98).

5.1.7.2 School-based surveys

All child-centred surveys are school-based, for which strong argument (in terms of sampling, design, financial efficiency, etc.) can be done. On the other hand, these surveys have the risk of excluding the most vulnerable. Children who are out of school (many Roma children in Europe for instance), not in mainstream school settings, are not captured by school surveys (Richardson 2012: 98).

5.1.7.3 Special groups/at-risk/most vulnerable groups of children

There are important groups of children, who are not or not properly represented in available statistics. Cross-country comparative administrative data are relatively scarce when child QoL domains are concerned and the most vulnerable groups of children (*e.g.* undocumented immigrants, street children) do not show up in these statistics (EU Task force, 2008; TÁRKI-Applica, 2010; TÁRKI, 2011). Household surveys, as well as adult surveys collecting household level information (like the EU-LFS) also have some important shortcomings as the full coverage of children is concerned. In general, the sample realisation of these surveys tends to be biased against both tails of income distribution, but especially the lower one. Children in private households at high risk of social exclusion, like those having migrant background, being travellers or of Roma ethnic origin, might be underrepresented in such surveys due to this bias. Even if they participate in the survey, a relatively large share of them cannot be properly identified (hard-to-identify groups). In a few Member States, specific information

systems (based on administrative/registers data or surveys) on children in vulnerable situation exist (EU Task force, 2008: 72).

Further, the sampling frame includes private household only and usually is taken from population registers of which up-to-datedness and reliability may greatly vary across countries. This procedure excludes not only the already mentioned vulnerable groups of children, but institutionalised children as well.

5.1.8 Supporting Member States to participate in international child surveys to promote full country coverage in certain QoL domains

Surveys, which are at the base of child-centred, non-material and outcome indicators for domains 'education', 'health and risk behaviour', and 'social connectedness and civic participation' are not part of the ESS (with the exception of PISA). The whole child monitoring process would benefit if the European Commission were more strongly involved in these data collections in order to improve country coverage and harmonisation in background variables.

PIRLS and TIMSS are relatively weak in country coverage. Some countries are missing (like Bulgaria, Estonia, Greece and Cyprus in the 2011 wave of TIMSS; Estonia, Greece, Cyprus, Latvia, Luxembourg, in the 2011 wave of PIRLS), and in a few cases (like Belgium or the United Kingdom) countries are represented by only one (Flanders for Belgium in TIMSS and Wallonia in PIRLS) or more (England and Northern Ireland for the UK in both surveys) regions, implying an obvious restriction to the comparability of results. We should mention here that the EU Member States-coverage of these surveys has improved during their lifetime and even compared to the previous waves in the mid-2000s. PISA has an almost full coverage of the EU Member States, only Cyprus and Malta are missing from the survey.

Neither the health and risk behaviour surveys, namely the HBSC and the ESPAD, provide full coverage of the EU Member States. In the HBSC, Belgium and the UK are represented by regions: French and Flemish parts of Belgium, and England, Scotland and Wales, respectively. In the case of the ESPAD, Belgium was represented by Flanders, while Germany by five *Bundesländer*.

Finally, as was mentioned above, the ICCS, the only survey on children's civic participation, covers only 22 Member States.

5.1.9 Supporting the harmonisation of socio-demographic and socio-economic items in international child surveys to better account for the social gradient in child outcome indicators

First, following the implementation plan presented in the ICP, we strongly recommend that the following breakdowns be applied in each case where relevant: (i) sex, and (ii) social background. The latter is indispensable if we aim at reflecting on the differences in outcomes according to the socio-economic status of individuals, parents or households. We also suggested for consideration in each and every case the (i) age in those cases when age sub-groups represent markedly different stages of life cycle from the point of view of the indicator (*e.g.* young people's employment rates for those aged 18-24 and 25-29); (ii) household structure: number of household members, household type, number of parents or children; (iii) the labour market position: *e.g.* employment status at individual level, work intensity at household level; (iv) migrant status. In the Child module,

- for household level, EU-SILC based indicators, we included household type, highest education of parents, poverty status and work intensity status, where relevant (for example, obviously, work intensity status was not used for the low work intensity indicator);
- for survey-based indicators in the domain 'education', the economic, social and cultural status index is applied, which is supplied by the data owners on each of the three surveys (PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS);

- for child-centred indicators of health and risk behaviour, as well as of social connectedness and participation, providing age and sex breakdowns is a baseline: in the case of the HBSC-based measures the age breakdown is provided separately where relevant, but the main breakdown is the one jointly provided for age and sex; in addition, the family affluence scale index is also provided. In the case of the ESPAD survey, sex and FAS, while in the case of the ICCS sex and parental education are provided separately;
- in his recommendations, Richardson puts a strong focus on the harmonisation of socio-demographic and socio-economic measures (Richardson, 2012: 111-113). For the socio-demographic measures he suggests age, sex, family form and migrant status to be harmonised across child surveys. Among socio-economic measures to be harmonised, he lists deprivation, parental education and parental employment.

We would strongly carry further Richardson's recommendation, by proposing to the EC to facilitate the coordination across the relevant surveys, also in order to make these breakdowns compatible with its own statistical requirements. While sex and in a way or another age are available on all of the surveys, family form and social-economic items are more problematic. Parental education and parental employment are present in all major surveys, excepting PIRLS, although the latter is less used and should be harmonised as an indicator. In the case of composite indicators of socio-economic status or of child deprivation, harmonisation is more difficult to achieve.

5.1.10 Strongly considering the launch of a sustainable and good quality longitudinal data collection in the Member States

Previous works in the field, which formulated recommendations on the data infrastructure (EU Task Force, 2008; TÁRKI-Applica, 2010; TÁRKI, 2011) stressed the importance of panel data. Even if the overwhelming majority of the indicators to monitor children's QoL are drawn from cross-sectional data, longitudinal surveys or individual level anonymised administrative data could have a remarkable value added. On the one hand these data can contribute to the indicator development process by establishing causal relationship between resources or inputs in early life stages and outcomes in later childhood or in adulthood. On the other hand, this contribution can be direct by providing specific indicators for monitoring. The longitudinal database of the EU-SILC, relying on a rotating design is an important tool in this respect, but has very strong limitations and can be used only to get better indicators on the resources side (*e.g.* persistent at-risk-of poverty rate). The four-year time period for which one quarter of the sample can be followed, is too short to link inputs with outcomes. It should be made clear that analysis of the long-term development of children and monitoring of truly outcome-based indicators both require monitoring over a far longer time period than could ever be offered by the rotating panels of EU-SILC (TÁRKI, 2011: 106). For the moment, only a few national level cohort studies (for examples see EU Task Force, 2008: 73) and household surveys (*e.g.* the German Socio-Economic Panel Survey or the British Household Panel) are able to provide an opportunity for such analyses. In many cases, longitudinal datasets are linked to administrative/register data, which provides a powerful tool to measure the long-term impacts of childhood on later outcomes and to study the mechanisms of intergenerational transmission of poverty (EU Task Force, 2008: 73-74). Their scope and validity is restricted, however, and cannot assist national level policies in other countries - even though their extensive use provides important, indispensable and partly generalisable research outcomes, also suitable for policy action.

Undoubtedly, building, maintaining and using longitudinal data is costly and therefore a cost-benefit analysis should be needed (EU Task Force, 2008: 74). The European Commission has already taken action in this field by funding a pilot project for a longitudinal data collection among children, called

MYWEB under the 7th Framework programme.⁵ The aim of the project is to assess the feasibility of a European Longitudinal Study for Children and Young People.⁶

5.2 Youth

In line with the recommendations stated by Gábos and Kopasz (2015) in their report on the child module for IPOLIS, we focus on three aspects of recommendations to the European Commission: (a) the lack of, and need for, the extension of indicators within domains and components; (b) the extension of the survey population to hard-to-reach young people; and (c) the consideration of longitudinal data. In addition to these three points, we start by discussing more general difficulties or challenges of monitoring youth that relate to the transitions from youth to adulthood.

5.2.1 Challenges of monitoring youth (in) transitions

Youth is a phase in life that is characterised by transitions into adulthood. The ‘big five’ transitions that are considered as most important are:

- a) leaving the parental home and forming an independent household;
- b) obtaining education and qualifications;
- c) entering the labour market;
- d) forming partnership and marriage, and;
- e) becoming a parent.

Each of these transitions bears its own risks and can fail. Monitoring the extent to which these transitions are successfully mastered can thus be considered relevant information for monitoring youth. Although youth indicator systems do provide information that directly or indirectly relate to these transitions, thus far they do not address these transitions as such.

Moreover, the fact that this period is one of transitioning from economic dependency to independence complicates matters when aiming to monitor youth well-being based on survey data. This is particularly the case for leaving the parental home and forming an independent household, which is not only an important transition in its own right, but has consequences for all indicators that refer to the household level. This is the case for almost all indicators in the domain of ‘*Material living conditions*’ (see for example, the discussion for the indicator of home ownership above). Some youth might still live with their parents, while others already live independently. In the first case, household-related indicators such as poverty and material well-being reflect the conditions of the parental household and thus, the socialisation of the youth. In the second case, the indicator reflects the living condition of the young person as an independent young adult. However, these two situations can give a very different picture for the same person right before and after leaving the parental home. A young person from a very affluent family might leave the parental home for university studies. When surveyed right before leaving, this young person appears to live in a wealthy household with high incomes, wealth, and material living conditions. When surveyed right after leaving the parental home, the same young person might be found on rather low incomes and in a small apartment with no wealth (i.e. in poverty and material deprivation). This is likely to be the case in many European countries, where the time of higher education studies is still considered as a period of ‘deferred gratification’. Above and beyond this tradition, the stage of attaining higher education or vocational training is oftentimes economically precarious. As human capital theory states, human capital accumulation is an investment that comes at the expense of current consumption for the sake of future consumption. As such, the material living conditions during this period can lead to false conclusions about

⁵ <http://www.mmuperu.co.uk/projects/measuring-youth-wellbeing-myweb>

⁶ For more details see the presentation of Christopher Fox (Manchester Metropolitan University) at the expert workshop on Framework and methods for indicator building for various vulnerable groups, held in Budapest, on 27-29 November 2013.

youth well-being and future life chances. In other words, taking the data and indicators as they are, it is likely that we overestimate the extent of poverty and material deprivation of young adults in Europe. At the same time, we probably underestimate the extent to which youth poverty is actually related to parental background, and thus, impacts on future life chances (for the case of Germany, see Groh-Samberg & Voges, 2014).

There is no simple solution to this. However, one possibility that we highly recommend is to provide - whenever possible - breakdowns for all indicators by 'living with at least one parent' and 'living independently'. So far, however, this breakdown is not considered for indicator systems on youth. In many datasets, this information is either missing or complicated to compute. Moving even beyond this, we recommend including (proxy) information on parental background in European surveys for young people living independently. If this information would be available, breakdowns of indicators of youth well-being by parental background would become possible. Finally, information on inter-generational support (in both directions, from parents to children as well as from children to parents) is highly relevant in this regard.

5.2.2 Extension of youth monitoring in terms of lack of indicators and further disaggregation of indicators

The potential pool of policy-relevant, timely, cross-country comparable, and robust indicators is large and the underlying data infrastructure is rich in regard to most of the quality of life domains (e.g. 'Material living conditions', 'Labour market attachment and work-life balance', and 'Education and training'). In the case of the domains and components regarding 'Health and risk behaviours', 'Social connectedness and civic participation', as well as 'Environmental quality and physical safety', the indicator coverage and the data infrastructure are poorer. For all domains, however, gaps can be identified and thus the monitoring of the youth can be improved. We list the most relevant gaps by domain and provide some recommendations for improving the monitoring of youth where possible. Additionally, we discuss the relevance of additional disaggregation of indicators.

5.2.3 Domain 'Material living conditions'

As mentioned above, little information and ready-to-use indicators can be found on the formation of independent households among youth. This includes indicators concerning sharing of income and expenditure among households and between households, which would serve to view the extent of (in)dependence of households and members of households. This also leads back to the question of whether poverty thresholds based on household income and expenditure are sufficient for conveying intra-household inequalities, even though disaggregated by sex. A threshold based on individual income or consumption could be considered. However, there is a lack of consensus on the definition of consumption and a lack of surveys which collect household or individual-level consumption information. Moreover, information on the extent to which household expenditures are shared among households and household members is also limited. In line with the 2010 EU-SILC module such information could be measures at least ones.

5.2.4 Domain 'Labour market attachment and work life balance'

An indicator on the employability of youth, or the extent to which skills that youth bring to the labour market are those that are demanded by employers, would shed light on the question of the link between supply and demand. However, the measurement criteria for the employability of youth are difficult to determine.

As reconciling work and family life has become a major public policy concern in many countries, indicators on (shares of) responsibility for family care (i.e., child and elder care) and household work,

as well as flexible hours, could improve the policy assessment of work-family issues. These would extend beyond caring for children since other family members may also require care, in relation to material living conditions.

5.2.5 Other domains

Research related to other domains revealed that existing data lacks information on components like early childhood education (domain: 'education and training'), bullying and fighting (domain: 'health and risk behaviours') on peer relationships for youth (domain: 'social connectedness and civil participation').

5.2.6 Further disaggregation of indicators

One main issue to improve upon would be the extent to which existing data on youth can be disaggregated to subnational levels, or by urban and rural residence. Of particular interest would be, for instance, the rate of growth in youth employment or indicators on environmental quality, such as pollution, noise, or crime among youth in urban and rural areas. However, possibilities for disaggregating existing data to sub-national levels are limited.

Unfortunately, not only sub-national level disaggregation proves to be problematic in the case of the youth. The set-up and the use of IPOLIS database has highlighted that the use of adult surveys in assessing the quality of life of young people in certain domains has serious limitations when analysis aims going beyond descriptives for the total young population or assessing differences by sex. With a few exceptions among EU member states (*e.g.* Germany, France, Spain, Poland), the young cohort sub-samples are too small to provide robust estimates in sub-groups like income quartiles or those defined by parental education, but the same is true when young cohorts are divided in narrower age-groups. There is a need, therefore, for (at least time-to-time) enlarged sub-samples of young people on the major cross-country comparative surveys in the European Union, which allows for a much-detailed analysis of underlying social processes.

5.2.7 Extending youth monitoring to hard-to-reach young people

The sampling frame includes private households only and is usually taken from population registers, of which currency and reliability may greatly vary across countries. This procedure excludes hard-to-reach youth populations. Hard-to-reach groups like migrants, refugees, displaced young persons, street youth, indigenous and minority youth, rural youth, and young people with disabilities are under- or unrepresented in most survey samples, even though they are often strongly affected by poverty or social exclusion.

5.2.8 Considering longitudinal data collection on the youth

Former work on youth has stressed the importance of panel data. Longitudinal surveys or individual-level anonymised administrative data could add remarkable value. Repeated information on individuals can contribute to the indicator development process by establishing relationships between resources or inputs in early life stages and outcomes in later life stages. The longitudinal database of the EU-SILC, for instance, could be used to measure such indicators.

5.3 Elderly

A significant improvement in monitoring the situation of the most vulnerable has taken place over the past decades in Europe, due to better coordination, in-depth research and an improved data infrastructure. Setting up the Elderly module of the IPOLIS, however, revealed some shortcomings of this monitoring system. In what follows, we summarise our main findings and make some recommendations for further improvements in the measurement of older people's quality of life.

In the selection of indicators for the Elderly module of IPOLIS, we used surveys conducted in the total population. We could not use the only survey of older adults (50+), SHARE, because of its relatively poor country coverage. As was seen, EU-SILC and EU-LFS served as the main data sources for the Elderly module of IPOLIS. Indicators for the domains 'Material living conditions' and 'Environmental quality and physical safety' were derived from EU-SILC, while indicators for 'Labour market attachment and work-life balance' and 'Education and training' from the EU-LFS. Besides these data sources, EQLS provides data for the domain 'Social connectedness and civic participation'. EHIS is the main source of data in regard to the domain 'Health and risk behaviour'. However, it is important to stress that EHIS data for all MSs will be available only from the current round onwards. Finally, some indicators were derived from the ESS and the ICT.

5.3.1 Encouraging the extension of monitoring of older people in terms of quality of life domains and components

When building the Elderly module of IPOLIS, we found that there is a large pool of policy relevant, timely, cross-country comparable and robust indicators in regard to some quality of life domains (*e.g.* 'Material living conditions' and 'Health and risk behaviours'). In the case of some other domains (*e.g.* 'Social connectedness and civic participation' and 'Environmental quality and physical safety'), the indicator coverage and the data infrastructure seem to be poorer. For all domains, however, smaller or larger gaps can be identified and thus the monitoring of older people's quality of life can be improved. In what follows we make recommendations regarding the indicators as well as the underlying data infrastructure. The recommendations are listed by domains of QoL.

5.3.2 Material living conditions

Our recommendations are related to the components of 'Material deprivation' and 'Housing'. According to research findings, measures of material deprivation appear to work less well for the older age group (than for families with children) (McKay, 2008; Guio *et al.*, 2012). For example, some of the items being asked about appear to be less relevant for the older age group (McKay, 2008; Guio *et al.*, 2012). In addition, older people are less likely to say they cannot afford an item they lack, and more likely to say they do not want it (McKay, 2004; Guio *et al.*, 2012). These findings might suggest that further work is needed on this issue, potentially including the development of age-specific indicators for measuring material deprivation.

Some of the regular indicators measuring housing conditions are less relevant for older people than for the other vulnerable age groups (*e.g.* overcrowding and severe housing deprivation). On the other hand, there is a need of specific indicators for measuring housing conditions of older people. One such is physical accessibility of basic services (*e.g.* public transport, food shop, etc.), which is essential for the elderly to live an independent life and actively participate in society. Currently, we lack such regular indicators and the underlying data. Although, the special Housing module of EU-SILC 2007 contained a couple of questions about the accessibility of public transport, grocery services, primary health care services, etc., these have not become part of the core questionnaire.

5.3.3 Education and training

Lifelong learning, a subcomponent of ‘access to and quality of education’ is of key importance for the old age group. This is measured by the proportion of those (aged 55 to 64) who received education or training in the four weeks preceding the survey. The indicator is derived from EU-LFS. We support the recommendation made by Eurostat (2010) that this measure should be improved upon by extending the learning to include more informal training, and by lengthening the period of reference to the last six months or last year.

5.3.4 Social connectedness and civic participation

The ‘Social connectedness and civic participation’ domain of IPOLIS encompasses relationships with family members and friends as well as different forms of civic participation: voting, group membership and volunteering, and internet use for civic participation. Indicators and the underlying data are missing or inappropriate in regard to relationships with family members (especially care provided to children/grandchildren or to the elderly or disabled relatives) and relationships with friends. The main data source for these indicators is the EQLS. This survey asks questions on social connections but data cannot always be compared across waves due to modifications in the questionnaire (*e.g.* questions on care to children/grandchildren and care to elderly or disabled relatives or questions on participation in civic and political actions). Another problem with EQLS and with other surveys of total population is that the size of the elderly subsample may be too small to provide breakdowns by socio-demographic variables.

5.3.5 Environmental quality and physical safety

This is probably the domain we know the least about, especially the ‘environmental quality’ component. The key sources of information on local environments are EU-SILC and EQLS. Both surveys have their own weaknesses. Exposure to air pollution cannot be assessed separately from other environmental problems based on the EU-SILC questions. At the same time, the EQLS asks about a series of environmental complaints, and even includes a question about the access to recreational or green areas. However, in some cases, there are modifications in the questions from wave to wave.

5.3.6 Extending the monitoring of older people to the ‘oldest old’

The EU-SILC covers the population living in private households, while a significant part of the ‘oldest old’ lives in communal establishments (*e.g.* old-age homes, long term care facilities, etc.). There are at least two problems arising from this. Firstly, this may lead to biased estimates of indicators, depending on the share of those living in communal settings and on the differences in the main socio-demographic characteristics of those living in private households and communal establishments. Therefore, we propose an in-depth cross-country analysis on how and to what extent indicator estimates for older people based on such surveys are biased due to the fact that the probability of living in a communal establishment is increasing with age. We suggest disseminating data derived from the EU-SILC (and other surveys sampled on private households) with an upper age limit of 85. Secondly, no cross-country information is available on the quality of life of institutionalised elderly people. We recommend that the monitoring of older people should be extended to those living in communal establishments.

5.3.7 Supporting Member States to participate in SHARE to promote full country coverage in certain QoL domains

As was already mentioned, SHARE would be an appropriate source of information in some domains (*e.g.* social and family networks), but it provides data far not for all Member States. Therefore, we recommend that the European Commission encourage and support Member States to participate in SHARE. The use of SHARE for monitoring the quality of life of older people instead of total population surveys would allow providing breakdowns by socio-demographic variables. Also, the full country coverage would greatly contribute to better monitoring of EU policies in relation to the elderly.

5.3.8 Supporting the harmonisation of data infrastructure regarding the QoL of older people

Finally, we recommend that a task force should be established to ensure that the requirements defined for the measures of a particular indicator system are fully met. These are: the indicators should be timely and regular. The latter requirement also means that it is important that the content of the indicator be constant in time (*e.g.* in the case of some EQLS questions, as mentioned above), and certain questions included in ad-hoc modules of EU-SILC be part of the monitoring system (*e.g.* the above questions in the Housing module should be part of the core questionnaire). Full coverage of Member States is another important criterion. Finally, the harmonisation of the socio-economic characteristics of individuals and households across surveys would also contribute to a better monitoring of the quality of life of the elderly.

5.4 The Roma

5.4.1 Baseline surveys are still needed

It is clear that there are some inherent challenges related to statistical data collection on the Roma population all over Europe. The main barrier to statistically appropriate Roma surveys is the lack of proper baseline statistics adequate to construct representative samples for each Member State; thus Roma surveys in general cannot meet all the requirements of representativeness. One of the main reasons for the lack of such baseline statistics is the protection of sensitive data, including data on ethnicity in EU countries in general. Furthermore, the lack of consensus among scholars, politicians and lawyers on the central question of ‘Who are the Roma?’ also hampers the elaboration of proper Roma surveys. In general, potential data sources of proper indicators, based on statistical data in the field of Roma inclusion, should meet the followings requirements:

- they should be based on representative sampling;
- they should be comparable across countries;
- they should be comparable with non-Roma/total population;
- the sample size should be sufficient for the Roma subsample;
- they should be available in all/most Member States.

Ideal data sources are national censuses, cross-country Roma surveys like the FRA/UNDP surveys (but only if it is possible to create from these Roma surveys general, widely used indicators that are designed for the overall population) and large-scale comparable EU surveys such as EU-LFS or EU-SILC (if a variable on (multiple) ethnicity or Roma identity is available).⁷ The main reason why

⁷ This is the recent practice (since 2014) of the Hungarian Central Statistical Office. Even if the Roma are still underestimated according to these variables, this practice is a forward-taking one and might be suggested for a wider use in other member states.

the Roma should be included in such large-scale EU surveys is that they are the only minority group that can be found in almost all EU Member States, and most of them - in whatever country - live in poor and vulnerable conditions; therefore involving them in these surveys would be meaningful.

5.4.2 Sufficient detail and breakdowns are required for the Roma as well

Moreover, ideal datasets provide both individual and household data: some of the relevant domains require household-level information, and in some cases, such as income or work intensity, individual information on all household members (or just those of active age) is also required. A very detailed suggestion for the indicators to be collected can be found in the relevant methodological paper of the InGRID project (Bernát and Messing, 2016)

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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